

Book Recommendation System Using Collaborative-Filtering System

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Abstract — Book recommendation system here uses collaborative filtering approach to recommend books of similar types. Collaborative filtering is an approach to build recommendation engines which is widely used in data mining and information retrieval. The recommendation system in the proposed system uses Memory based collaborative filtering. Based on a collection of user preferences, memory-based collaborative filtering (CF) creates suggestions for objects. This strategy is based on the notion that an active user's interests will be more likely to match those of other users who share similar preferences as the active user.

Keywords - Machine Learning, Book recommendation system, Collaborative filtering, Memory-based collaborative filtering, Item Based collaborative filtering.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recommendation systems are increasingly being utilised to help users find the most relevant internet content. Content-based (CB), collaborative filtering (CF), and hybrid recommendation systems are the three types of recommendation systems. For large and complex data, CF methods frequently gives better performance and accuracy than any other Recommendation System techniques. Collaborative filtering is used by most websites, including Amazon, YouTube, and Netflix, as part of their sophisticated recommendation engines. This method can be used to develop recommenders that provide recommendations to customers based on what other users like and dislike.

Collaborative techniques are of 3 types : Memory-based, Model-based and Hybrid based collaborative filtering technique. Here we implement our book recommendation system by Memory based also known as Neighborhood based collaborative technique. Hence, the choice and computation of a similarity measure between users is critical to rating items.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A lot of research has been done to predict books of similar types from user. Some references are :

[1] Yunkyong Lee, illustrates a detailed study of collaborative filtering model and its types that comes under

[2] recommendation system and diving deep into model based collaborative filtering systems, compares model based and memory based systems and its working differences.

[3] Fethi Fki, Similarity measurement algorithms that are used in memory based collaborative filtering model.

[4] Le Nguyan Hoai Nam presented a memory-based collaborative filtering technique for predicting items that users expect. It has two phases: in the offline phase, it calculates the preference similarity between each pair of users, and in the online phase, it predicts an active user's rating for a target.

[5] Yan-ni Chen and Min Yu suggested a user-item-based collaborative filtering algorithm. Using a novel similarity measure method, this strategy integrated the benefits of user-based and item-based algorithms to estimate the target item rating.

III. METHODOLOGY

In the realm of recommendation systems, collaborative filtering is a well-known technology. There are two types of collaborative filtering systems: user-based and item-based. We use an item-based collaborative filtering approach in this proposed system. From an open site we use csv files as the dataset. The details about items ie;books, information about user and ratings from user about a particular books are all specified aspart of dataset.Name of a books from the dataset is entered asinput to get suggestions about other books that are similar tobook user has entered. Collaborative Filtering mainly involves 3 steps:

Step1 - Collecting user rating data matrix

Step2 - Selecting similar neighbors by measuring rating similarity

Step3 - Generating predictions

Figure1: Flow Chart of the proposed system

A. Prepare the Dataset

First we prepare our dataset to find its size ,check whether there is any missing values and the presence of any duplicate values.

B. Models Selected

Memory Based Collaborative Filtering

Memory-based Collaborative Filtering approaches employ historical data from user ratings to determine the similarity of users or products and recommend the most comparable.

Item Based Collaborative System

Item-based collaborative filtering attempts to forecast items by comparing them to other objects linked with the user.

Let's imagine that Item A and C are nearly identical. IBCF has the ability to recommend Item C to a user who enjoys Item A. Collaborative filtering requires a set of things that the target user has already assessed to determine similarities

between items and a target item. The system then makes predictions for the target item based on item similarities and the target user's previous preferences.

Figure2: Working of Item-based Collaborative Filtering

The memory-based method assesses the similarity between two users or products, then uses the weighted average of all the scores to make a prediction for the user. The computation of similarity between objects or users is a key aspect of this method. This is done using a variety of methods, including Pearson correlation and vector cosine based similarity.

The Pearson correlation similarity of two users x, y is defined as:

$$r = \frac{\sum (x - m_x)(y - m_y)}{\sqrt{\sum (x - m_x)^2 \sum (y - m_y)^2}}$$

Figure3: Pearson correlation equation to find distance between two users

Another approach, is calculating similarities between pair of items are using cosine similarity metric.

The item-based CF approach's use of the cosine similarity metric ignores variations in user ratings. By deducting the relevant user's average rating from each co-rated pair, adjusted cosine similarity balances out this downside and is described as below.

$$\text{similarity} = \cos(\theta) = \frac{\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\|\mathbf{A}\| \|\mathbf{B}\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n B_i^2}}$$

Figure4: Vector Cosine Equation to represent distance between two similar vectors.

This method uses cosine of angle between two vectors A and B with start point in the zeros of coordinate axes.

Figure5: Angle Distance representation between two similar vectors

The algorithm for item based collaborative filtering is as follows:

- Step 1:** Find the relationship between pairs of items.
- Step 2:** Users interest is predicted using rating matrix with user preferences.

C. OUTPUT (RECOMMENDATIONS)

A rule set is created when the system is trained using the above techniques using a 'training set,' and when 'user attributes are entered into the model, these features' are processed according to the established set of rules.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULT

Here, we use item based collaborative filtering to recommend books which are similar to user inputs. By using similar metrics such as Cosine Similarity from sklearn, as the metric to compute the similarity between books.

```
recommend('Message in a Bottle')  
[['Nights in Rodanthe',  
 'Nicholas Sparks',  
 'http://images.amazon.com/images/P/0446531332.01.MZZZZZZZ.jpg'],  
 ['The Mulberry Tree',  
 'Jude Deveraux',  
 'http://images.amazon.com/images/P/0743437640.01.MZZZZZZZ.jpg'],  
 ['A Walk to Remember',  
 'Nicholas Sparks',  
 'http://images.amazon.com/images/P/0446608955.01.MZZZZZZZ.jpg'],  
 ["River's End",  
 'Nora Roberts',  
 'http://images.amazon.com/images/P/0515127833.01.MZZZZZZZ.jpg']]
```

V. CONCLUSION

Collaborative filtering algorithms are most commonly used algorithms in Recommendation System. Due to wide usage of internet a large amount of data is generated and it has become a tedious task for user to find their preferences. Users preferences for items are stored in the form of rating matrix which are used to build relation between the user and items to recommend items of users interest.

VI. REFERENCES

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